

Envisioning the Future of Infrastructure as Code Leveraging Generative AI within DevSecOps Online Appendix

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I. EMPIRICAL VALIDATION

To assess whether GAI models can generate more efficient IaC scripts than human experts, we designed experiments along all the DevSecOps stages. Our null hypothesis is that GAI models, powered by RAG and fine-tuning methods, can retrieve IaC scripts more efficiently, secure, and adaptable than those generated by humans, based on previous experience in other SE fields [1], [2].

In each stage, we will compare IaC scripts generated by GAI models with those designed by experienced DevOps engineers. We focus on metrics such as correctness, adherence to best practices, security compliance, and responsiveness to changes. These experiments will employ appropriate IaC platforms for each stage and choose the best GAI models for handling the tasks, including state-of-the-art models.

As a rule of thumb, we can not blindly trust a single model's output. Therefore, this section will propose different models to compare and cross-validate GAI outputs to strengthen our envisioned approach.

We fine-tune or employ RAG throughout the experiments to improve their domain-specific knowledge and real-time data integration. We train the models on infrastructure configuration datasets and security best practices during fine-tuning [1]. RAG models enable access to external knowledge bases and documentation during generation, making their outputs more accurate and contextually appropriate [2].

In the **Planning** stage, we feed user stories, requirements, and architecture diagrams into GAI models such as GPT-4 and OpenAI's Codex, as well as Google's PaLM and Microsoft's Turing-NLG. We will explore where fine-tuning the models or providing examples via RAG changes the model's performances. We can target IaC tools such as Terraform and AWS CloudFormation because of their significant capabilities and industry-wide adoption [3]. We will compare the generated scripts to those created by human engineers regarding how well they fit the project requirements, scalability, and security guidelines.

During the **Coding** stage, the GAI models update the IaC scripts regarding changes made to the source code and configuration files. Those artifacts are processed by models allowing

code understanding, such as OpenAI's Codex DeepMind's AlphaCode or Meta Llama. Models create the scripts based on Ansible and Chef, among others, showing the code changes and dependencies. The comparison has been made regarding the accuracy of the updates and consideration of security issues, leveraging outputs from static analysis tools.

In the **Building** stage, we address the polyglottism challenge [4] by testing the proficiency of GAI models to handle projects in multiple languages. We feed models with build scripts, dependency graphs, and Software Bills of Materials (SBOMs). We aim to generate IaC scripts for the building process; thus, we focus on containerization features and utilize platforms like Docker and Kubernetes. Resource utilization and efficiency of the scripts generated by GAI and those from human experts are compared.

In the **Testing** stage, we feed test cases, expected test results, and evaluation metrics to GAI models. The generated IaC scripts should be able to provision the required testing environments, leveraging environment setup utilities such as Vagrant and Puppet. The experiments for this stage should focus on how the generated scripts can satisfy testing needs and incorporate security mechanisms, especially concerning dynamic application security testing tool outputs.

During the **Releasing** and **Deploying** stages, GAI models should optimize deployment scripts and ensure enforcements of secure releases are developed. From release notes to deployment manifests to version control tags, GPT-4 and IBM's Project Debater-type models can generate or refine IaC scripts to perform the deployment using platforms like Helm and Kubernetes. We can evaluate the scripts on metrics and indicators such as deployment success rate, security compliance to standards such as CIS Benchmarks, and the need for manual intervention.

In the **Operating** and **Monitoring**, models dynamically modify the IaC scripts during the operation and monitoring stages by constantly analyzing real-time monitoring data, logs, and performance metrics. GAI models can also further integrate monitoring tools such as Prometheus and Grafana and recommend modifications in infrastructure toward better performance and security. We will compare the effectiveness and speed of these models against human operators at making

such adjustments, particularly in response times to incidents and proactive ability.

This comprehensive assessment aims to determine whether GAI models would have better infrastructure management by automatically creating IaC scripts than traditional methods. In addition, we want to validate that GAI can deliver secure and adaptable infrastructure configurations based on how GAI-generated scripts perform compared to human experts using several metrics.

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